

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART VII *. SOME OBSERVATIONS ON THE
COPE-KNOEVENAGEL CONDENSATION OF ETHYL CYANOACETATE
WITH ETHYL, 2-METHYL-2 β -CARBETHOXYETHYL, *cyclo*PENTA-
NONE AND THE STEREOCHEMISTRY OF THE
REDUCTION PRODUCT

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The stereochemistry of the cyanoacetic ester derivative (III), described in Part I, has been established by conversion to the *cis*-ketone (IX). The abnormal product, reported earlier, has been fully characterised and its structure established.

In Part I of this series (Mukharji, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 91) the preparation of the cyanoacetic ester derivative (III) was described. This was obtained by reduction of the corresponding unsaturated compound (II) with aluminium amalgam and from the above saturated derivative, (III), the synthesis of the tricyclic compounds (VI and VII) was carried out. The stereochemical course of the entire reaction sequence depends on the stereochemistry established during the reduction of the unsaturated ester (II) to the saturated ester (III).

The choice of the particular synthetic approach, described in Part I, was influenced by the observation of Linstead that reduction of ethyl (2-methyl-2-carbethoxy)-*cyclo*-pentylidene-cyanoacetate (IV) with aluminium amalgam furnished the *trans*-isomer of the corresponding dihydro-ester (V) (Errington and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 666). We anticipated similar course in our compound to yield the *trans*-isomer of (III), thereby establishing the *trans* configuration in the union of the C/D rings in our synthetic system, identical with that present in natural steroids. The experiments described in the present communication, however, confirm that the reduction of (II) leads exclusively to the *cis*-isomer of (III), and in view of this result the synthetic approach, described in Part I, is of no value for the total synthesis of steroids. The work reported in this paper was completed some years back, but publication had been delayed due to some unavoidable difficulties.

The saturated cyano-ester (III) (Mukharji, *loc. cit.*) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to the dibasic acid (VIII: R=H) which proved to be completely homogeneous. It was next converted into the diethyl ester (VIII: R=Et) and then subjected to the Dieckmann condensation with sodium dust in anhydrous benzene. The resulting β -keto-ester was hydrolysed to the hydrindanone (IX). This ketone readily furnished a semicarbazone, m.p. 191-92° and a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 125-26°.

A ketone of this structure, provisionally assigned the *cis* configuration but without any proof, had been described by McQuillin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1097). They prepared it by catalytic reduction of the enone (X) and

* Continuation of Part I.

characterised it by a semicarbazone, m.p. 191°. Although a direct comparison was not made, the two ketones, obtained differently, appeared to be identical. An authentic synthesis of *cis*-8-methyl-5-ketohydrindane has been described recently by Conroy (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3045) which he characterised by a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 126-28°.

Through the courtesy of Dr. Conroy we were able to secure a sample of his derivative and compare it with ours. A mixed melting point determination of the two hydrazones did not show any depression of melting point and confirmed the identity of the two ketones. The *cis* configuration of our ketone was thus established and, hence, that of the cyano-ester (III).

In Part I it was also mentioned that during condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with the keto-ester (I:R=Et) in presence of ammonium acetate, an abnormal product (m.p. 121°) was obtained besides the normal condensation product (II). This was a highly crystalline nitrogenous substance, which gradually turned into a brown oil and finally polymerised on standing. The structure of this compound, as represented by (XI), has been established through the following observations :

(a) The compound, which was neutral, analysed for $C_9H_{13}ON$.

(b) Hydrolysis with dilute acid afforded 2-methylcyclopentanone-2 β -propionic acid (I:R=H), identified as the semicarbazone of its ethyl ester (II:R=Et) and direct comparison with an authentic sample.

(c) The same compound was formed when the keto-ester (I:R=Et) was heated with ammonium acetate and acetic acid in benzene solution under identical conditions.

(d) It could be prepared by hydrolysis of 2-methyl-2 β -cyanoethylcyclopentanone (XIII) with 80% sulphuric acid at room temperature, the intermediate amide undergoing ring-closure to yield (XI) (cf. Albertson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3816; Bruson and Reiner, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 214).

The above facts, however, do not permit of an unequivocal decision between the two possible alternative structures (XI and XII) for this compound. A decision in favour of (XI) was obtained through study of the infra-red spectra of the compound. It showed a sharp band at 2.95 μ and a very strong band at 6.05 μ , characteristic of an amide with a free-NH group, and another band at 6.1 μ for the -CH=CH-NH-group.

The ultraviolet spectra of the compound showed a maxima at 238 m μ (log ϵ , 4.04). $\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated amines generally show absorption maxima around 228-236 m μ , indicating that the amino group possesses conjugating power, similar to -C=C- by interaction of the unshared electron pair on nitrogen with the π -electron of the double bond (Braude, *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 42, 105; Bowden, Braude, Jones and Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 45; Bowden, Braude and Jones, *ibid.*, 1946, 948; Herr and Heyl, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3627; 1953, 75, 1918). Very recently Leonard and Locke (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 438) have studied the ultraviolet maxima of a number of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated amines and reported the maxima of a very similar compound as ours, 1-*n*-butyl-2-methyl- Δ^2 -pyrroline (XIV) at 238 m μ .

If Woodward's rule (*ibid.*, 1942, 64, 72) be extended to these compounds, the calculated value for the compound (XI) should be about 243 $m\mu$, corresponding to a bathochromic shift of 5 $m\mu$ due to an exocyclic double bond. The observed value of 238 $m\mu$ is certainly due to acylation of the nitrogen in (XI) which produces this hypsochromic shift due to the opposing effect created by participation of the nitrogen electron pair with the carbonyl group in amide resonance. In β -amino-crotonic ester (λ_{max} , 274 $m\mu$) the absorption maxima is shifted to 269 $m\mu$ in the corresponding N-acetyl derivative (Banerjee, Sen*Gupta and Das Gupta, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 1516).

The formation of such byproducts is due to the interaction of free ammonia from ammonium acetate with the carbonyl group (Weiss, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 200, 5193) and such products have subsequently been reported by various other investigators (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 443; Banerjee, Sen Gupta and Das Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

The preparation of the keto-ester (I:R=Et) has been simplified and considerably improved upon by monocyanoethylation of 2-methylcyclopentanone in presence of a few drops of 40% methanolic KOH (Frank and Pierle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 724). This preparation will be reported in detail by one of us (N.K.C.) separately. The yield in the Cope-Knoevenagel condensation of the keto-ester (I:R=Et) with ethyl cyanoacetate was considerably improved by employing Caroge's modification (Caroge, Roble and Sprauge, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 1388).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-methyl-2β-carbethoxyethylcyclopentylidene-cyanoacetate (II) was prepared according to Carce's modified method in a better yield than previously obtained (Mukharji, *loc. cit.*).

A solution of 2-methyl-2β-carbethoxyethylcyclopentanone (I:R = Et; 29.7 g., 0.15 M), ethyl cyanoacetate (34 g., 0.3 M) and acetic acid (7.5 g., 0.12 M) in benzene (60 c.c.) was heated under reflux, fitted with a Dean-Stark water separator. Ammonium acetate (9.5 g., 0.12 M) was added in five equal instalments at an interval of 4 hours. After addition of the last portion of the catalyst, the mixture was refluxed for further 8 hours, then cooled, washed several times with water, concentrated and distilled under reduced pressure. After a forerun of unchanged components, the solid byproduct (2.5 g., b. p., 130°-150°/1 mm.) distilled over, followed by a colorless viscous oil (23 g.) which was collected, b.p. 165-67°/1 mm. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 240 m μ (log ϵ , 4.1). (Found: C, 65.25; H, 8.01; N, 4.61. C₁₆H₂₃O₄N requires C, 65.53; H, 7.85; N, 4.78 per cent).

2-Methylcyclopentane-1-acetic-2β-propionic Acid (VIII:R=H).—The saturated cyano-ester (III, 7.5 g.) was hydrolysed with HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) for 45 hours under reflux. On cooling, crystals separated which were collected by filtration. After one crystallisation from dilute acetic acid it had m.p. 152-53°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 61.82; H, 8.50. C₁₁H₁₈O₄ requires C, 61.68; H, 8.41 per cent).

cis-8-Methyl-5-ketohydrindane (IX).—The above dicarboxylic acid (4 g.) was converted into its diethyl ester in the usual way and the ester (4 g.) was purified by distillation, b. p. 133-36°/1 mm. This diester (4 g.), dissolved in a little anhydrous benzene, was added to a suspension of sodium dust (prepared from metallic sodium, 0.5 g.) under anhydrous benzene (25 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed under nitrogen until all sodium particles had disappeared. It was cooled, acidified with iced HCl and the benzene layer removed. The residue left on removal of the benzene developed an intense blue colour with ferric chloride in alcohol.

The above crude β-keto-ester was hydrolysed with 10% HCl (10 c.c.) for 15 hours at reflux. The solution was cooled, saturated with salt and extracted several times with ether. On removal of the ether and distillation, the ketone could be obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. 100°/6 mm., yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 78.71; H, 10.43. C₁₀H₁₆O requires C, 78.95; H, 10.52 per cent).

The *seymicarbazone* after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 190-91°. (Found: N, 20.18. C₁₁H₁₆ON₂ requires N, 20.09 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 125-26° and did not depress the melting point of an authentic specimen, m.p. 126-28°, supplied by Dr. Conroy. (Found: N, 16.70. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N, 16.87 per cent).

4-Aza-5-keto-8-methyl- $\Delta^{3:0}$ -hydrindane (XI) was obtained as a byproduct in the Cope-Knoevenagel condensation, as described earlier. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-60°) containing a little benzene, m.p. 121-22°; $\lambda_{\text{MAX}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 238 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.04). (Found: C, 71.31; H, 8.9; N, 9.46. $C_9H_{13}ON$ requires C, 71.52; H, 8.61; N, 9.27 per cent).

When a mixture of the keto-ester (I: R=Et; 7.5 g.), acetic acid (1.8 c.c.) and ammonium acetate (4 g.) in benzene (15 c.c.) was heated for about 30 hours and the mixture worked up as before, this product (ca. 1 g.) was obtained and after crystallisation from petroleum ether-benzene mixture had m.p. 121-22° alone and on admixture with the sample obtained during condensation, described earlier.

2-Methyl-2-cyanoethylcyclopentanone (10 g.) was treated with 80% H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) with efficient stirring and at such a rate that the temperature did not rise above 45°. After stirring it at room temperature for another 5 to 6 hours, the mixture was left overnight and then poured into crushed ice, and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with dilute bicarbonate solution, water, dried and concentrated. This was then distilled under reduced pressure when the fraction boiling at 135°-140°/1 mm. crystallised in the receiver; upon crystallisation from petroleum ether-benzene mixture it had m.p. 121-22°, both alone as well as on admixture with the sample described above.

The byproduct (5 g.) was hydrolysed with HCl (10 c.c.) for about 10 hours. The organic matter was isolated in the usual way and converted into its ethyl ester, as described before. The semicarbazone, m.p. 80-81°, obtained from this preparation was identical in all respects with the semicarbazone of authentic 2-methyl-2 β -carboethoxyethylcyclopentanone (Mukharji, *loc. cit.*).

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